

Alternative gravity theories

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Abstract: The gravitational field can not only generate gravitational force but also repulsive force. Besides universal gravitation, there exists universal repulsion between objects. Universal repulsion is dark energy. Whether an object experiences gravitational or repulsive force is determined by the velocity difference in the same or opposite direction between the object and the gravitational field. The velocity of the gravitational field is the speed of light. Other objects can only be affected by the acceleration of the gravitational field when it passes through them. The gravitational field is a kind of wave. The universe was born in the Big Bang and will end in the Big Collision. Light travels more slowly in regions with stronger gravitational fields.

Keywords: Modified gravity; gravity; Dark matter; Dark energy; Cosmology

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I. Introduction

Modern physics holds that the universe originated from a Big Bang. I call this universe the Big Bang universe. Imagine you are an arrow capable of traversing time and space, flying perpendicular to the time dimension in one direction with infinite speed. You arrive outside the edge of the Big Bang universe. What would you see?

The universe originated approximately 13.8 billion years ago from a Big Bang. Modern physics suggests that before the Big Bang, there was no time.

But you have indeed traveled back to before the Big Bang. If there was no time before the universe's Big Bang, then the singularity could have exploded at any moment. So why did it happen 13.8 billion years ago?

When you travel back to before the universe's Big Bang, back 13.8 billion years ago, what would you see?

Why is dark energy in the universe approximately more than twice the amount of matter (including dark matter), but within a galaxy, matter (including dark matter) is hundreds of thousands of times more abundant than dark energy?

What existed before the birth of the universe?

What is outside the universe?

Why does dark energy seemingly increase out of nothing?

Humans are three-dimensional beings; how can you comprehend four-dimensional space?

How can you comprehend higher-dimensional spaces?

Does modern physics believe that three-dimensional beings can only understand three-dimensional space? Do those of you who support using higher-dimensional spaces to explain three-dimensional phenomena do so because you can already perceive four-dimensional space, five-dimensional space, and even higher dimensions?

II. Overview of Gravity

Gravity is a fundamental force in nature that determines the interaction between matter. In General Relativity, gravity is described as the curvature of spacetime; matter experiences gravity by moving along geodesics in this curved spacetime. The production of gravity occurs because objects emit a gravitational field.

III. Overview of Dark Matter

Dark matter is a type of matter that does not emit light and interacts very weakly with electromagnetic waves. Its existence is inferred from dynamical effects observed in the large-scale structure of the universe. For example, observations of galactic rotation speeds indicate that the visible matter within galaxies cannot provide sufficient gravitational force to bind them, thus requiring the existence of large amounts of dark matter to explain the observations. Furthermore, the formation and evolution of large-scale structures strongly depend on the presence of dark matter. To explain dark matter, I have modified Newton's theory of universal gravitation.

IV. Overview of Dark Energy

Dark energy is a mysterious force causing the accelerated expansion of the universe. Its existence is inferred through observations of distant supernovae and the cosmic microwave background radiation, among other methods. According to observations, dark energy constitutes about 68.3% of the total energy content of the universe, far exceeding the contribution of visible matter and ordinary matter. The nature of dark energy is still poorly understood, but it is generally thought to be possibly related to vacuum energy or some new physical field. I believe dark energy is produced by the gravitational field.

V. Proportion of Various Components in the Universe

The observed components of the universe consist of approximately 4.9% visible matter (the

matter constituting stars, planets, gas, and dust) or "baryons", 26.8% dark matter, and 68.3% dark energy.

VI. Efficiency of Acceleration Variation with Velocity Difference

The acceleration experienced by an object depends on the velocity difference between the accelerating substance and the object, the amount of the accelerating substance, and the mass of the object. When the velocity difference between the accelerating substance and the object is in the same or opposite direction and reaches the speed of light, the efficiency of the acceleration experienced by the object is the greatest. The speed of electromagnetic waves, electromagnetic fields, and gravitational fields is the speed of light.

The acceleration formula under field action is as follows.

$$a = A \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{V - c}{c}\right)^2}$$

a is the acceleration experienced by the moving object due to the field. A is the acceleration experienced by the stationary object due to the field. c is the speed of light. V is the co-directional or counter-directional velocity difference between the object and the field. The speed of gravitational, electric, and magnetic fields is the speed of light.

VII. Formula for the Action of the Gravitational Field on an Object

$$a = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{V - c}{c}\right)^2} (1 + \gamma R) \frac{Gm}{R^2} \cos \frac{\pi V}{c}$$

a is the acceleration experienced by the moving object due to the gravitational field. m is the mass of the object emitting the gravitational field.

G is the gravitational constant. R is the distance from the center of mass of the object emitting the gravitational field. V is the co-directional or counter-directional velocity difference between the object and the gravitational field. γ is a constant. π is the pi constant. c is the speed of light.

When $0 < V < 0.5c$, the object experiences a repulsive force.

When $0.5c < V < 1.5c$, the object experiences an attractive force.

When $V = 0.5c$, the object experiences no force.

When $V = 0$, the object experiences no force.

When $V = 1.5c$, the object experiences no force.

When $V = 2c$, the object experiences no force.

When $1.5c < V < 2c$, the object experiences a repulsive force.

VIII. The Birth and Death of the Universe

Outside our Big Bang universe, there are countless other Big Bang universes, and these universes will collide with each other. After collision, they form a core, which absorbs matter from the surrounding universes, growing larger and larger. Once the core has absorbed sufficient matter, it undergoes a Big Bang, forming a new universe.

IX. The Propagation of Light in a Gravitational Field

When light propagates, the denser the medium, the slower its speed. A gravitational field is also a kind of medium; similarly, light travels more slowly in regions where the gravitational field is stronger, rather than time passing more slowly.

$$v = \frac{xGcm}{R^2}$$

v is the speed of light in the gravitational field. x is a constant. G is the gravitational constant. c is the speed of light in a vacuum. m is the mass of the celestial body emitting the gravitational field. R is the distance between the photon and the center of mass of the celestial body emitting the gravitational field.

X. Conclusion

Gravity, dark matter and dark energy are all reactions of the gravitational field. Dark energy is actually the repulsive force produced by the gravitational field. Dark matter comes from the attractive force generated by the gravitational field. Light travels more slowly in regions with stronger gravitational fields..

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替代引力理论

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摘要: 引力场除了产生引力还能产生斥力。物体之间除了存在万有引力,还存在万有斥力。万有斥力就是暗能量。引力场和物体的同向或反向的速度差决定物体受到的是引力还是斥力。引力场的速度是光速。引力场要穿过其他物体时,其他物体才能受到引力场加速度。引力场是一种波。宇宙诞生于大爆炸,毁灭于大碰撞。引力场越强的地方光传播得越慢。

关键词: 修正引力; 引力; 暗物质; 暗能量; 宇宙学

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一、引言

现代物理学认为宇宙起源一次大爆炸。我把这个宇宙叫做大爆炸宇宙。假如你是一把能穿越时间和空间的箭，垂直于时间向一个方向穿梭飞行，你的速度无限。你来到了大爆炸宇宙的边缘以外你会看到什么？

宇宙大概起源于 138 亿年前的一次大爆炸，现代物理学认为宇宙大爆炸之前是没有时间的。但是你确实回到了大爆炸之前。如果宇宙大爆炸之前是没有时间的，那奇点随时爆炸都可以，可是为什么是 138 亿年前？

当你穿梭飞行回到宇宙大爆炸之前，回到 138 亿年前 你会看到什么？

为什么暗能量在宇宙中大约是物质（包括暗物质）2 倍多。但是在一个星系中的物质（包括暗物质）是暗能量的数十万倍？

宇宙诞生前是是什么？

宇宙之外是什么？

暗能量为什么会凭空增加？

人是一个三维空间的生物，你又如何了解四维空间？你又如何了解更高维的空间。

现代物理学认为三维空间的生物只能了解三维空间吗？难道你们这些支持用更高维空间来解释三维空间的现象，是因为你们已经能感受到四维空间，五维空间，及更高维的空间了。我是感觉不到。

二、引力概述

引力是一种自然界的基本力，它决定了物质之间的相互作用。在广义相对论中，引力被描述为时空的弯曲，物质通过沿着弯曲时空的测地线运动来体验引力。引力的产生是因为物体发射了引力场

三、暗物质概述

暗物质是一种不发光且与电磁波相互作用极弱的物质。它的存在是通过观测宇宙大尺度结构中的动力学效应而推断出来的。例如，星系旋转速度的观察结果表明，星系中的可见物质无法提供足够的引力来束缚星系，因此需要存在大量的暗物质来解释观测结果。此外，大尺度结构的形成和演化也强烈依赖于暗物质的存在。为了解释暗物质我修改了牛顿的万有引力理论。

四、暗能量概述

暗能量是一种导致宇宙加速膨胀的神秘力量。它的存在是通过观测遥远的超新星和宇宙微波背景辐射等手段推断出来的。根据观测结果，暗能量占据了宇宙总能量的约 68.3%，远远超过

了可见物质和普通物质的贡献。目前对暗能量的本质仍知之甚少，但一般认为它可能与真空能或某种新的物理场有关。我认为暗能量是引力场产生的。

五、宇宙各种成分占比

人类所观察到的部分宇宙的物件大约是由 4.9%的可见物质（构成恒星、行星、气体和尘埃的物质）或“重子”，26.8%的暗物质和 68.3%的暗能量构成。^[1]

六、加速度随速度差的变化效率。

物体受到的加速度取决于靠什么加速的物质与物体的速度差和加速物质的量以及物体的质量。加速的物质与物体同向或反向的速度差在光速时物体受到的加速度效率最大，而不是物体速度越大质量就越大。电磁波，电磁场，引力场的速度为光速。

场作用下加速度公式如下

$$a = A \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{V - c}{c}\right)^2}$$

a 是物体运动时受到场产生的加速度。 A 是物体静止时受到场产生的加速度。 c 是光速。 V 是物体和场的同向或反向的速度差。引力场，电场和磁场的速度是光速。

七、引力场对物体的作用公式如下

$$a = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{V - c}{c}\right)^2} (1 + \gamma R) \frac{Gm}{R^2} \cos \frac{\pi V}{c}$$

a 是物体运动时受到的引力场作用的加速度。 m 是发射引力场物体的质量。 G 是万有引力常数。 R 是距离发出引力场物体质心的距离。 V 是物体和引力场的同向或反向的速度差。 γ 是常数。 π 是圆周率。 c 是光速。

$0 < V < 0.5c$ 时物体受到的是排斥力， $0.5c < V < 1.5c$ 时物体受到的是吸引力。 $V = 0.5c$ 时物体不受力， $V = 0$ 时物体不受力， $V = 1.5c$ 时物体不受力。 $V = 2c$ 时物体不受力。 $1.5c < V < 2c$ 时物体受排斥力

八、宇宙的诞生与消亡

大爆炸宇宙之外还有无数的大爆炸宇宙，这些宇宙都会相互碰撞。碰撞之后形成一个核，这个核吸收周围宇宙的物质，然后越吸越多。等核吸收了足够的物质之后，核会发生大爆炸形成新的宇宙。

九、光线在引力场中的传播

光传播时，介质密度越大，光传播得越慢；引力场也是一种介质，同理引力场越强的地方光传播得越慢；而不是引力场越强的地方时间越慢。

$$v = \frac{xGcm}{R^2}$$

v 是引力场中光的速度, x 是常数, G 是万有引力常数, c 是无介质中光的速度, m 是发出引力场天体的质量。 R 是光子和发出引力场天体之间的距离。

十、结束语

引力, 暗物质, 暗能量都是引力场的一个反应。暗能量其实就是引力场产生的排斥力。暗物质来自引力场产生的吸引力。引力场越强的地方光传播得越慢。

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